

Enhancing DIY musical instruments with custom circuit boards

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Abstract. *This paper explores the use of bespoke printed circuit boards (PCBs) for enhancing Do-It-Yourself (DIY) making of electronic sound devices. With the tools and manufacturing costs now within reach of amateur makers, the production of PCBs for DIY projects can add stability and reproducibility to the growing number of custom instruments used in ubiquitous music projects. The article discusses the impact of maker culture on the custom development of electronic musical instruments, and how incorporating PCB design can extend these developments. Several case studies are described and lessons from these for DIY makers are outlined.*

Resumo. TBA

1. Introduction

In recent years the process of having custom printed circuit boards manufactured has become more accessible with free open-source tools and inexpensive production of small runs. These developments bring the process within the reach of DIY electronic instrument makers, including the authors.

Our objectives are similar to others in the Ubiquitous Music (UbiMus) community; to enable access to music making using affordable and non-complex technologies (Lazarini et al. 2020, Brown et al. 2018, Schmeder and Freed 2009). A tension when trying to promote access to music making is that one barrier may simply be replaced by another. This could be the case, for example, when moving from acoustic to electronic instruments as acoustic instrumental skill requirements are replaced by the need for engineering skills. We feel that the barrier to entry for PCB design and production has reached a point where its value is worth the additional investment in skills.

PCBs can be useful for any electronic circuit but provide most utility for moderate to complex ones. In any case, PCB production requires prior developmental steps that are already part of DIY audio electronic workflows. Software-based prototypes are often a starting point for instrument development (Lazarini et al. 2015), they are then typically prototyped on a solderless breadboard with components later soldered together for use in workshops and performances. The reliability of handmade devices made through this process is quite variable, depending on the engineering skills of the maker. We have found that the use of custom PCBs has made our DIY instruments more reliable for performance, and construction in maker workshops easier and faster.

2. Background

The making of DIY instruments has a long history as summarised by Timoney et al. (2020). The more recent history of DIY electronic music making has been greatly influenced by the publication of the book *Handmade Electronic Music* (Collins 2006/2009/2020). Microcontroller platforms such as Arduino and Raspberry Pi have been central to enabling these activities since their introduction in the mid 2000s. More recently music-specific design such as Bela (McPherson and Zappi 2015) and Daisy¹ underscore the popularity of DIY audio. A wide variety of sensors can be integrated into circuits for various types of gestural or environmental control over audio signals. In addition to DIY activities, the development of new electronic musical instruments using these materials has been the focus for academic explorations as presented in the *New Interfaces for Musical Expression* conferences, and elsewhere, since the turn of the century. Music and sound related projects have been a staple of maker workshops and of introductory coding courses in both community and educational settings (Tanenbaum et al. 2013).

2.1. DIY and Maker cultures for music

Music composers in the 20th century began the turn to everyday objects for music making. Examples include John Cage's use of paper, screws and other objects for prepared piano works and his use of radios, watering cans and kitchen appliances as sound sources. Since the 1990s the DIY movement in electronic music making has adopted arts and craft approaches to working directly with materials for the making of sound devices and new instruments. These activities have benefitted from a broader push for reducing the costs of small-run electronics, and the accessible production of custom PCBs is part of that trend.

PCB-based kits, such as the Atari Punk Console from Yeovil Hacker Space (Whiteford 2015) have been the basis for community music workshops. Thus far, these have typically been designed and created by relative experts for use in community situations and reveal the potential for the extended use of PCB by amateur engineers, as advocated for in this article.

DIY electronic music tends to focus on live music making using handmade instruments. Often these are noisy or low-fi—partly out of necessity given the materials available—but this has often become a deliberate aesthetic choice and stylistic characteristic. As technologies have improved and costs reduced, the devices made by DIY music makers have expanded in sophistication and musical scope. The access to small-run PCB manufacturing is another step in this evolution.

2.2. Accessible tools and services

The manufacturing of PCBs for electronic music is not new. PCBs were used in the earliest commercial synthesizers from the 1970s and one look at the prevalence of modular synth components, each of which includes a PCB, shows their commercial ubiquity. There is even a strong hobbyist market in the design and distribution of PCBs for music devices on sites such as SynthCube² or Nonlinear Circuits³ and by

¹ <https://www.electro-smith.com/>

² <http://synthcube.com>

³ <https://www.nonlinearcircuits.com/>

organisations such as Dirty Electronics (Richards 2013a). Like many technologies, the printing of circuit boards has recently become much more refined and inexpensive, although it is still not trivial. A range of low-cost tools and services has made this possible.

The manual production of PCBs by hobbyists has been possible in the past, but the etching process involves toxic chemicals and can be messy, if not dangerous. Outsourcing production to professional PCB manufacturing opens up the process to many more makers.

The tools and manufacturing support for PCBs have become more accessible. Free software for PCB design includes Fritzing⁴ and KiCad⁵. DIY makers may already be using Fritzing for designing or documenting breadboard electronics, and these projects can be extended to PCB design as well. KiCad is an open-source project for designing schematics and circuit boards. It is a bit more complex than Fritzing, but also has more features. The applications KiCad and Eagle were used for the case study examples in this article.

Having designed the PCB using software tools, these can be exported to Gerber files for sending a professional PCB manufacturing service such as PCBWay (China), OSHPark (USA), AISLER (Germany) and more. A price comparison from various international manufactures can be accessed at PCBShopper.com. Production and shipping typically take about two weeks.

2.3. PCBs for DIY

There are some considerations for utilising PCBs in a DIY electronic music making process, compared to their use in commercial settings. Simpler boards will use through-hole components, like those used for breadboards, so the PCB layout needs to allow spacing for ease of hand soldering by non-experts. Automated assembly of surface-mounted components is also possible and reduces hand soldering but adds some complexity to the design process. Establishing optimal circuit tracks between components can take some time, but fortunately PCB design software often includes auto-routing tools, and free external tools such FreeRouting⁶ can be very useful.

There are many online resources to assist with undertaking the process of PCB design and manufacture. While a full tutorial is well beyond the scope of this article, to give the reader a feel for the process here are the basic steps involved.

- 1) Prototype the project on a breadboard.
- 2) Draw a schematic in software.
- 3) Use the schematic to design a PCB layout.
- 4) Route connections between components and establish a ground plane.
- 5) Export Gerber files.
- 6) Upload files to a PCB manufacturer and place an order.
- 7) Solder components onto the delivered PCB.

⁴ <https://fritzing.org/learning/tutorials/designing-pcb/>

⁵ <https://www.kicad.org/>

⁶ <http://freerouting.org>

3. Exemplar projects

To illustrate what is possible we will describe three examples of music projects the authors have taken through to the stage of PCB design and build.

3.1. The Sonic Frisbee

The Sonic Frisbee (Figure 1) is a six-voice portable and battery-powered synthesiser based around a CMOS 40106 (Hex Schmitt-Trigger) and a LM386 (amplifier) integrated circuit (IC), there is no computer involved. This makes for a very low-cost instrument overall. It is designed for improvised real-time performance and the PCB is designed to facilitate hand-held interaction and gestural freedom.

Three of the synthesizer voices are operated via “resistive-touch” on the MuTec lettering where there is a physical gap in the signal path of each voice and oscillation only occurs when the gap is bridged. This element of the instrument is performed using fingers to touch metal pads so electricity flows across the gap and human flesh becomes part of the circuit. The result is a tactile but unpredictable relationship between human input and sonic output given that it is difficult to perform exact pitches but the sonic response to touch is instant. The remaining three voices are either controlled by a light dependent resistor (LDR) or a potentiometer.

The pitch range of each voice is switchable high/low, which can lead to dramatic shifts in musical character. LDR/pitch control is laid out horizontally across the board while output of the instrument is divided in half with two separate volume controls: one for the three touch-sensitive voices and the other for the three light/potentiometer voices. The three individual voices that make up each of the two halves of the instrument can either be mixed via diodes or resistors (switchable), this offers further timbral manipulation. Sonic output is switchable between a mono jack socket on the rear and the onboard amplifier/speaker combination. Power is provided by a 9-volt battery that clips into a socket on the rear, this also makes the instrument stable and sets the sit-angle towards the performer when used as a desktop instrument.

Figure 1. The Sonic Frisbee and its PCB layout

The design of the Sonic Frisbee was prototyped on a solderless breadboard and the PCB design was done in EAGLE⁷.

A significant advantage of the PCB design for this instrument, rather than alternative DIY methods of laser-cut box or solderable breadboard, was the combination of neatness and compact design. As can be seen in Figure 1, the wiring is quite complex, and the PCB provides a compact product easily manipulated in live performance without the risk of wiring disconnects.

3.2. The Beat Machine

The Beat Machine is a 16-step sequencer and 3-voice synthesizer controlled by 10 potentiometers, 19 buttons, and an accelerometer (Brown and Ferguson, 2020). The Beat Machine is designed to be hand-held, like the Sonic Frisbee, but can also be operated resting on a tabletop. The PCB facilitates a lightweight design that is compact enough to operate in the hands and movement-oriented features such as accelerometer control of parameters encourage expressive gestural performance.

The controls are connected to two Arduino Pro Micro microcontrollers that communicate via the I2C communications protocol, one microcontroller handles the sequencing and the other functions as a synthesizer using the Mozzi library (Barras 2020). There are three layers of control, one for each voice. Low-cost tactile switches are used to enter step-sequences and to access the various layers of control. A ring of programmable LEDs (light emitting diodes) indicates sequence pattern and layer information so the user can see where steps have been programmed to sound and which synthesizer voice these correspond to. The red voice is optimised for a bass drum-like tone (noise source has high frequency rolled off), the blue voice is optimised for a high-hat like tone (noise source has low frequencies rolled off), the green voice is full-range and is intended to approximate a snare drum.

Each synthesizer voice is made up of two elements that can be blended together or sounded in isolation using the balance control, the first is a sine waveshape and the second can either be a sawtooth waveshape or a noise source. When using sine and saw these can be detuned by up to an octave and then pitch-fall and the attack/release controls can be used to sculpt the overall sonic character of each voice. Pitch, volume, and distortion controls are also available, see Figure 2 for an overview.

⁷ <https://www.autodesk.com/products/eagle/free-download>

Figure 2. The Beat Machine and its software overview

A two-axis accelerometer on the rear of the beat machine is set such that the Y axis (forward and back) controls the chance of changing the probability of sequence steps, while the X axis (left and right) effects the blend between Osc. 1 and Osc. 2 and can thus be used as a timbral control. A video demonstration of the Beat Machine by students of 2710QCM Electronic Instruments class at Griffith University in 2021 is at <https://vimeo.com/534756472>.

The Beat Machine was prototyped on a large solderless breadboard and PCB design was done in EAGLE. However, the authors have since adopted KiCad as their preferred software for schematic design and PCB manufacture.

A significant learning from the development of the Beat Machine PCB was the need for attention to power circuit design. The combination of Neopixel LEDs and audio running on an Arduino microcontroller led to disruptions and audio crosstalk from power fluctuations. The PCB design enabled parallel power circuits and distributed decoupling capacitors throughout the board to keep sensitive and power-hungry elements apart.

3.3. The Micro Mono Control

During COVID-19 lockdowns in 2020 some music students we taught needed an inexpensive MIDI controller to continue their studies remotely. This prompted the design of the Micro Mono Control (MMC), the components for which cost around \$20 USD. The MMC is a MIDI controller with onboard monophonic synthesis capability (Figure 3). The MMC can be operated at rest on a desktop or held in the hands like a game controller. Serval continuous controllers—joystick, light sensitive resistor, and accelerometer—encourage real-time gestural interaction.

The MMC sends continuous control messages from 5 potentiometers, a light sensitive resistor (LDR), 6-axis accelerometer, and an XY joystick. It has 5 buttons that trigger MIDI note messages. The MMC includes a monophonic subtractive synthesizer and arpeggiator modified with the onboard controls or via external MIDI input. Audio level is set by a dedicated potentiometer and output is switchable between an onboard loudspeaker (buzzer) and 3.5mm audio output socket. The MMC is driven by an Arduino Pro Micro microcontroller running the USB-MIDI and Mozzi libraries⁸. It can be USB powered or run from batteries.

⁸ <https://sensorium.github.io/Mozzi/>

Figure 3. The Micro Mono Control and its PCB layout

The design of the MCC was prototyped on a solderless breadboard with programming done in the Arduino IDE⁹. Once the circuit was finalised, the PCB design was done in KiCad.

The PCB enabled the MMC to be both lightweight and robust. The fact that the board also acted as a case, especially for the joystick, minimised the number of fabricated parts required. Doubling down on featuring the PCB, the decision was made to go with a black colored PCB which looked more finalised and polished than the typical green or red PCBs that are typically designed to be out of sight inside a product.

4. Reflections on the exemplar projects

The design of PCBs for an instrument is a task that requires a solid background in breadboard prototyping. Although software applications, such as KiCad, include useful default settings that minimise decisions and have tools to check the validity of circuits, the PCB design process is somewhat abstract (being entirely digital) and is best grounded in an understanding of the breadboard prototyping activity.

Learning about PCB design process and software takes time but is rewarded with neat and robust infrastructure for novel electronic instruments. Iteration and mistakes are inevitable and need to be considered part of the design process. Printing PCB designs on paper for checking against component fit is a useful strategy to locate issues before manufacturing.

The use of PCBs implies that makers solder components to the boards. Often soldering is already part of DIY electronic music processes, but for those who may have only employed solderless breadboard circuit design processes the addition of soldering to PCB design skills may present an additional hurdle and/or learning opportunity.

While one aspect of the maker culture is to embrace technologies, there is also an undercurrent of technological critique in the DIY movement. For some, the use of

⁹ https://www.arduino.cc/en/Main/Software_

manufactured PCBs may be seen as giving into the professional and commercial world of technology, and they may prefer the deliberate messiness of roughly soldered components or even deliberately unruly PCB designs like those of Gijs Gieskes (2018). There is also the consideration of resource usage and environmental impact of the PCB manufacture and shipping to take into account.

5. Conclusion

This article has outlined a case for the addition of small-run PCB production as a viable addition to existing DIY electronic music making activities for use in UbiMus contexts. PCB design and manufacturer seem like a next-step skill for those looking to move beyond breadboard-based methods.

Three example projects were described that show some of the potential use of small-run PCBs. These examples were created by reasonably skilled individuals who were new to PCB design processes at the time. We suggest there is scope for digital fabrication processes, such as PCB manufacturing, to be further incorporated into bespoke instrument building processes, especially where outcomes require multiple devices as employed in workshop-based events and Do-It-Together (DIT) approaches to DIY advocated by Spencer (2008) and Richards (2013) and already a feature of many UbiMus activities.

References

- Barrass, T. (2020). *Mozzi*. <https://sensorium.github.io/Mozzi/>
- Brown, A. R., & Ferguson, J. (2020). Beat Machine: Embracing the creative limitations and opportunities of low-cost computers. *Leonardo Music Journal*, 30, 8–13.
- Brown, A. R., Keller, D., & de Lima, M. H. (2018). “How Ubiquitous Technologies Support Ubiquitous Music”. In L. Higgins & B.-L. Bartleet (Eds.), *The Oxford Handbook of Community Music* (pp. 131–151). Oxford University Press.
- Collins, N. (2006/2009/2020). *Handmade Electronic Music: The Art of Hardware Hacking*. Routledge.
- Gieskes, G. (2018). *Dirty Express*. <http://gijs.gieskes.nl/dirtyexpress/>
- Lazzarini, V., Keller, D., Kuhn, C., Pimenta, M., & Timoney, J. (2015). Prototyping of ubiquitous music ecosystems. *Journal of Cases on Information Technology*, 17(4). 13 Pages.
- Lazzarini, V., Keller, D., Otero, N., & Turchet, L. (Eds.). (2020). *Ubiquitous Music Ecologies*. New York: Routledge.
- McPherson, A., & Zappi, V. (2015). An environment for submillisecond-latency audio and sensor processing on BeagleBone Black. In *Audio Engineering Society Convention 138*. Audio Engineering Society.
- Richards, J. (2013). Beyond DIY in electronic music. *Organised Sound*, 18(3), 274–281.
- Richards, J. (2013a). *Dirty Electronics*. <http://www.dirtyelectronics.org/info.html>
- Schmeder, A., & Freed, A. (2009). A Low-level Embedded Service Architecture for Rapid DIY Design of Real-time Musical Instruments. *NIME*, 121–124.

- Spencer, A. (2008). *DIY: The rise of lo-fi culture*. London: Marion Boyars Publishers.
- Tanenbaum, J. G., Williams, A. M., Desjardins, A., & Tanenbaum, K. (2013). Democratizing Technology: Pleasure, Utility, and Expressiveness in DIY and Maker Practice. Proceedings of the SIGCHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems - CHI '13, 2603–2612.
- Timoney, J., Lazzarini, V., & Keller, D. (2020). “DIY electronics for ubiquitous music ecosystems”. In V. Lazzarini, D. Keller, N. Otero, & L. Turchet (Eds.), *Ubiquitous Music Ecologies* (pp. 52–70). Routledge.
- Whiteford, N. (2015). *Atari Punk Console Kit*.
<http://yeovilhackspace.org.uk/2015/11/29/atari-punk-console-kit-now-available/>